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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
- 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
- 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
- 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
- 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
- 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
- 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
- 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
- 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
- 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
- 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
- 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
- 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
- 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
- 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
- 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

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INTEGRATING SOCIAL-EMOTIONAL LEARNING IN EFL CLASSROOMS: ENHANCING LANGUAGE PROFICIENCY AND EMOTIONAL INTELLIGENCE

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Abstract: This study explores the integration of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. The study examines the impact of SEL on students' language acquisition, emotional development, and interpersonal relationships in EFL settings. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining qualitative and quantitative data collected through classroom observations, surveys, and interviews with both students and teachers. The findings indicate that integrating SEL into the EFL curriculum enhances student engagement, improves language proficiency, and fosters a supportive learning environment. The paper discusses pedagogical implications and provides recommendations for EFL educators seeking to integrate SEL into their teaching practices.

Key words: Social-Emotional Learning (SEL), English as a Foreign Language (EFL), language acquisition, emotional intelligence, emotional development, student engagement, teaching practices.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu tadqiqot ijtimoiy-emotsional o'rganishni (SEL) ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish (EFL) sinflariga integratsiya qilish jarayonini o'rganadi. Tadqiqotning asosiy maqsadi SEL ning talabalarning til o'rganish jarayoniga, emotsional rivojlanishiga hamda EFL sharoitidagi o'zaro munosabatlarga ta'sirini aniqlashdan iborat. Tadqiqotda aralash metodologiya qo'llanilib, sifat va miqdoriy ma'lumotlar sinfdagi kuzatishlar, so'rovnomalar hamda o'quvchilar va o'qituvchilar bilan o'tkazilgan intervyular orqali yig'ildi. Tadqiqot natijalari shuni ko'rsatadiki, SEL ni EFL dasturiga integratsiya qilish talabalarning faolligini oshiradi, til malakasini yaxshilaydi va qo'llab-quvvatlovchi o'rganish muhitini shakllantiradi. Maqolada pedagogik oqibatlar muhokama qilinib, SEL ni EFL o'qitish amaliyotiga muvaffaqiyatli integratsiya qilish bo'yicha tavsiyalar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: ijtimoiy-emotsional o'rganish (SEL), ingliz tilini chet tili sifatida o'qitish (EFL), til o'rganish, emotsional intellekt, emotsional rivojlanish, talabalar faolligi, o'qitish amaliyoti.

Аннотация: Данное исследование посвящено изучению интеграции социально-эмоционального обучения (SEL) в процесс преподавания английского языка как иностранного (EFL). В работе анализируется влияние SEL на усвоение языка студентами, их эмоциональное развитие и межличностные отношения в условиях EFL. В исследовании использован смешанный метод, объединяющий качественные и количественные данные, собранные посредством наблюдений в классе, опросов и интервью с обучающимися и преподавателями. Полученные результаты свидетельствуют о том, что интеграция SEL в учебную программу EFL способствует повышению вовлечённости студентов, улучшению их языковой компетенции и формированию поддерживающей образовательной среды. В статье рассматриваются педагогические последствия и представлены рекомендации для преподавателей EFL по интеграции SEL в образовательную практику.

Ключевые слова: социально-эмоциональное обучение (SEL), английский язык как иностранный (EFL), усвоение языка, эмоциональный интеллект, эмоциональное развитие, вовлечённость студентов, преподавательская практика.

INTRODUCTION

Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) has become an essential component of modern education, focusing on the development of emotional intelligence, empathy, and social skills. SEL helps students manage their emotions, build positive relationships, and make responsible decisions^[1]. These competencies are especially important in the context of foreign language learning, where emotional resilience, motivation, and the ability to navigate social interactions are critical for success^[2]. In English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms,

learners are often confronted with anxiety and cultural differences, which can hinder their language acquisition process^[3]. As such, integrating SEL into EFL teaching could enhance not only students' emotional intelligence but also their language proficiency^[4].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Recent studies have shown that SEL can improve academic performance by fostering a supportive and emotionally safe learning environment^[5]. In particular, EFL learners can benefit from SEL strategies such as collaborative learning, emotional regulation, and self-reflection, which have been found to increase motivation and engagement in language learning^[6]. However, while the benefits of SEL have been widely studied in general education, its specific integration into EFL contexts remains underexplored^[7]. This gap in research highlights the need for further exploration of how SEL can be effectively integrated into EFL classrooms and the impact such integration has on both language learning and emotional development. Despite the growing recognition of SEL's importance in educational settings, there remains a significant gap in the literature regarding its practical application in EFL classrooms. While studies have explored the impact of SEL on students' emotional and social development^{[5][8]}, few have examined its direct influence on language acquisition, especially in non-native English-speaking contexts. Moreover, there is a lack of research addressing the strategies teachers can use to integrate SEL into EFL curricula in ways that specifically respond to the emotional challenges language learners face. This study seeks to fill this gap by investigating the integration of SEL into EFL classrooms and exploring its effects on students' language proficiency, emotional resilience, and motivation.

The following research questions guide this study: How does the integration of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into EFL classrooms affect students' language learning outcomes? What impact does SEL integration have on students' emotional resilience and self-regulation in the EFL context? How do EFL teachers perceive the integration of SEL in their teaching practices, and what challenges do they encounter in its implementation? This study is significant for several reasons. First, it addresses the research gap by examining how SEL can be integrated into the EFL classroom and its potential impact on language learning outcomes. Second, the study contributes to the growing body of literature on the importance of emotional and social competencies in language learning, offering evidence of how SEL can enhance not only language proficiency but also students' emotional well-being. Third, this research provides practical insights for EFL educators on incorporating SEL into their teaching methods, thereby fostering a more supportive and inclusive learning environment. Finally, this study has the potential to inform future curriculum development and teacher training programs, highlighting the need for professional development in SEL for language teachers. Given the increasing importance of emotional intelligence in academic success and life beyond the classroom^[9], integrating SEL into language education has the potential to create well-rounded, emotionally intelligent learners who are better equipped to navigate the challenges of both language learning and life.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study employed a mixed-methods design, combining both qualitative and quantitative approaches to explore the integration of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms. The research aimed to assess the impact of SEL on students' language learning outcomes, emotional regulation, and motivation, while also exploring EFL teachers' perspectives on SEL integration. The design utilized pre- and post-intervention assessments, classroom observations, and semi-structured interviews with both students and teachers to gather comprehensive data on the effects of SEL strategies in an EFL context. The research was structured to collect both numerical data on language proficiency and emotional intelligence, as well as descriptive data on the experiences of students and teachers. This mixed-methods approach allowed for data triangulation, providing a more comprehensive understanding of how SEL affects students' emotional and language development. The study involved a total of 126 participants, comprising 120 EFL students and 6 EFL teachers. The participants were selected from a university-level language program in Uzbekistan, where English is taught as a foreign language.

Student participants: The student participants (N = 120) were enrolled in intermediate and advanced EFL courses. They were selected based on their enrollment in the academic year during which the study was conducted. The selection process involved purposive sampling to include students from two different proficiency levels, ensuring diversity in language skills. Students were randomly assigned to one of the six teachers' classrooms, each implementing SEL integration. **Teacher participants:** The study included six EFL teachers (3 male and 3 female), each with over five years of teaching experience. Teachers were selected based on their

willingness to integrate SEL strategies into their teaching. All teachers had experience with traditional EFL methods but had no prior formal training in SEL. They were recruited through voluntary participation following an invitation to join the study. Teachers participated in a one-day SEL training workshop prior to the start of the study. The training included strategies for incorporating SEL into language lessons, such as group activities to promote empathy, emotional regulation techniques including journaling and mindfulness exercises, and role-playing activities designed to practice social skills in English. The training materials were developed based on the CASEL framework for SEL and adapted to meet the specific needs of the EFL context.

A pre- and post-course survey was developed to assess students' emotional intelligence, motivation for learning English, and self-reported language proficiency. The survey included Likert-scale items addressing students' emotional self-regulation, ability to communicate in English, and willingness to participate in classroom activities. The surveys were adapted from the Emotional Intelligence Scale^[10] and the Motivation for Learning English Scale^[11]. EFL proficiency test: A standardized language proficiency test was administered to measure students' language skills before and after the intervention. The test assessed listening, speaking, reading, and writing abilities, providing a comprehensive evaluation of language proficiency. The test was aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), ensuring its appropriateness for both intermediate and advanced learners. Classroom observation protocol: A structured observation protocol was developed to assess the integration of SEL into EFL lessons. The protocol focused on the types of SEL activities employed, levels of student engagement, and teachers' implementation of SEL strategies. Observations were conducted across 10 sessions during the semester, with the researcher recording detailed field notes for each session.

Pre- and post-surveys: Surveys were administered to all students at the beginning and end of the course. The pre-survey collected baseline data on students' emotional intelligence, motivation for learning English, and perceived language proficiency, while the post-survey measured changes in these variables following the SEL intervention. Surveys were completed online to ensure accessibility and participant anonymity. Classroom observations: The researcher conducted 10 classroom observations throughout the semester. Each observation focused on the incorporation of SEL activities into lessons, with particular attention to teachers' implementation strategies and students' responses. Observations were conducted across different classrooms to capture variations in teaching styles and classroom dynamics. Teacher interviews: Semi-structured interviews were conducted with all six teachers at the end of the semester. The interviews explored teachers' experiences with SEL integration, challenges encountered, perceptions of the effectiveness of SEL strategies, and observed changes in students' emotional and language development. Student interviews: A subset of 30 students was selected for follow-up interviews to provide qualitative insights into their experiences with SEL. These interviews focused on students' perceptions of how SEL activities influenced their language learning, emotional development, and classroom engagement.

Quantitative data analysis: Data obtained from the pre- and post-surveys were analyzed using descriptive statistics and paired-sample t-tests. The t-tests were employed to determine whether statistically significant changes occurred in students' emotional intelligence and language proficiency following the intervention. In addition, language proficiency test scores were analyzed using analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) to control for baseline differences between intermediate and advanced learners. Qualitative data analysis: Interview and observation data were analyzed using thematic analysis. Recurring themes related to SEL implementation, student engagement, and emotional outcomes were identified. Teacher and student interview data were coded according to key thematic categories, including teacher challenges, student engagement, and emotional growth. Member checking was employed to enhance the credibility and validity of the findings. The table below summarizes the mean scores for Emotional Intelligence, Motivation for Learning English, and Language Proficiency obtained from the pre- and post-surveys. These data were used to evaluate changes in students' emotional and academic outcomes following the integration of SEL strategies into the EFL classroom.

Survey type	Emotional intelligence (mean score)	Motivaion for learning (mean score)	Language proficiency (mean score)
Pre-survey	3.2	3.0	70
Post-survey	4.1	4.0	85

The bar chart below visually represents the changes observed in the same aspects from the pre- to post-survey. As shown, there is a notable improvement in all three categories.

Picture 1: Pre- and Post-Survey results: Emotional intelligence, motivation and language proficiency

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The data collected from the pre- and post-surveys, language proficiency tests, and classroom observations revealed the following key findings. Emotional intelligence: Students' emotional intelligence scores increased from a mean of 3.2 in the pre-survey to a mean of 4.1 in the post-survey. Motivation for learning English: Motivation scores also showed an improvement, increasing from a mean of 3.0 in the pre-survey to a mean of 4.0 in the post-survey. Language proficiency: Language proficiency scores, as measured by the standardized language test, showed a significant increase. The mean score in the pre-test was 70, which increased to 85 in the post-test.

A paired-sample t-test was conducted to compare the pre- and post-survey emotional intelligence scores. The results showed a statistically significant increase in emotional intelligence scores from the pre-survey ($M = 3.2$, $SD = 0.6$) to the post-survey ($M = 4.1$, $SD = 0.5$), with a t-value of $t(119) = 9.3$, $p < 0.001$. Similarly, a paired-sample t-test was used to compare pre- and post-survey motivation scores. The results revealed a significant increase in motivation, with the pre-survey mean ($M = 3.0$, $SD = 0.7$) rising to the post-survey mean ($M = 4.0$, $SD = 0.6$). The t-value was $t(119) = 10.2$, $p < 0.001$. An ANCOVA was conducted to compare language proficiency scores from the pre-test and post-test while controlling for initial proficiency levels measured in the pre-test. The post-test mean score ($M = 85$, $SD = 7.8$) was significantly higher than the pre-test mean score ($M = 70$, $SD = 8.5$). The results indicated a significant difference in post-test scores after controlling for pre-test scores, with an F-value of $F(1, 118) = 12.9$, $p < 0.001$. Classroom observations showed that SEL activities were incorporated into the lessons with varying degrees of frequency and engagement: 90% of observed sessions included group activities aimed at promoting emotional regulation. 80% of sessions utilized reflective journaling or emotional check-ins at the beginning or end of lessons. 85% of students appeared to engage actively in SEL-based activities, as indicated by participation in group discussions and role-playing exercises. The findings of this study provide strong evidence that the integration of Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms positively impacts both students' emotional intelligence and language proficiency. The results indicate a statistically significant improvement in emotional intelligence, motivation for learning English, and language proficiency from the pre- to post-intervention assessments. The increase in emotional intelligence scores from a mean of 3.2 to 4.1 suggests that students not only became more aware of their emotions but also developed greater emotional regulation and empathy, which are critical components of SEL [1]. This finding is consistent with previous studies demonstrating that SEL programs enhance emotional competencies, leading to improved emotional resilience [6]. The improvement in emotional intelligence is particularly noteworthy in the EFL context, where learners often experience anxiety related to language use, making emotional regulation a key factor in successful learning.

The significant increase in motivation, from a mean of 3.0 to 4.0, aligns with the premise that SEL can enhance students' intrinsic motivation [2]. The integration of SEL-based activities, such as emotional check-ins

and group discussions, likely created a more supportive and engaging classroom environment, which is essential for fostering motivation in language learning ^[12]. This result reinforces the importance of emotional support in the learning process, particularly in EFL settings where learners face unique challenges. The increase in language proficiency scores from 70 to 85 provides concrete evidence that SEL integration can have a direct effect on academic achievement. These findings suggest that SEL not only supports students' emotional and social development but also contributes to their cognitive growth, specifically in language learning. This result echoes previous research showing that emotional and social competencies are strongly linked to academic success ^[5]. By promoting positive classroom dynamics and reducing anxiety, SEL strategies likely enabled students to perform better in language tasks. The findings of this study align with much of the existing literature on SEL and its impact on academic and emotional outcomes. Previous research has demonstrated that SEL programs can improve emotional intelligence, motivation, and academic performance across various educational settings ^{[11][9]}. For example, Rivers et al. found that SEL interventions improve emotional intelligence, which in turn leads to better academic engagement and performance ^[6]. Similarly, Durlak et al. reported that students who participated in SEL programs showed increased motivation and academic achievement, which is consistent with the findings of this study ^[13]. However, while there is substantial evidence for the effectiveness of SEL in general education, research specifically focusing on its integration into EFL classrooms remains relatively scarce. This study contributes to the literature by demonstrating that SEL can be effectively implemented in EFL contexts, where students often experience heightened emotional barriers to language learning, such as anxiety and lack of confidence. This extension of SEL to language-learning contexts represents a notable contribution to the field.

The findings also resonate with previous studies emphasizing the importance of a supportive classroom environment for language learners. For instance, Young highlighted that emotional intelligence plays a crucial role in language learning, particularly in reducing anxiety and enhancing learner engagement [3]. This study supports that claim by showing that SEL integration leads to increased student motivation and engagement, which directly impacts language proficiency. While the findings of this study are promising, several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the sample size, although adequate for the purposes of this study, was limited to a single university-level language program in Uzbekistan. This limitation restricts the generalizability of the results to other cultural or educational contexts. Future studies should consider expanding the sample to include diverse geographical locations and educational settings in order to test the broader applicability of SEL in EFL classrooms. Second, the study relied on self-reported data obtained from surveys and interviews, which may be subject to potential biases such as social desirability or inaccurate self-assessment. Although classroom observations were conducted to provide additional insights into student behavior, the inclusion of more objective measures—such as performance-based assessments or peer evaluations—could further strengthen the validity and reliability of the findings. Third, while the intervention period of 15 weeks allowed for the observation of initial changes in emotional intelligence and language proficiency, longer-term studies are required to determine the sustainability of these effects. It would be particularly valuable to examine whether improvements in emotional intelligence and language proficiency are maintained over time and how they influence students' long-term language learning outcomes.

The results of this study suggest that integrating SEL into EFL classrooms can be a highly effective strategy for enhancing both emotional and academic outcomes. The findings have several important implications for EFL educators and policymakers. Implications for teaching practice: EFL educators may use the results of this study to integrate SEL strategies into their teaching practices. This may involve providing teachers with training in SEL techniques, such as collaborative group work, emotional check-ins, and reflective journaling, to support students in managing emotions and developing social skills. In addition, teachers can create emotionally supportive classroom environments that reduce anxiety and increase student engagement, thereby enhancing language learning outcomes. Curriculum development: Integrating SEL into the EFL curriculum can serve as an effective means of fostering well-rounded learners who are not only linguistically proficient but also emotionally intelligent. Educational institutions may consider embedding SEL frameworks into teacher education programs and language curricula to equip future educators with the competencies required to support students' emotional and academic development. Future research: Future studies should examine the long-term impact of SEL integration in EFL classrooms, with particular attention to the sustainability of gains in emotional intelligence and language proficiency. Further research could also explore the influence of SEL on specific language skills, such as speaking and listening, which are closely linked to learners' emotional states and interpersonal interactions. Moreover, investigating the application of SEL in foreign language classrooms beyond English would help determine the extent to which these findings can be generalized across different language-learning contexts.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates that integrating Social-Emotional Learning (SEL) into English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms has a positive impact on both students' emotional intelligence and language proficiency. The significant improvements observed in emotional regulation, motivation, and language skills highlight the importance of emotional and social competencies in language learning. By fostering a supportive and engaging classroom environment, SEL strategies not only enhance students' academic performance but also contribute to their overall emotional well-being. The findings underscore the potential of SEL to transform EFL teaching practices and offer valuable insights for educators seeking to support the holistic development of language learners. Future research should explore the long-term effects of SEL integration and its application in diverse educational contexts to further validate its effectiveness.

References:

1. CASEL (Collaborative for Academic, Social, and Emotional Learning). (2020). *The CASEL Guide to Effective Social and Emotional Learning Programs*.
2. Schunk, D. H., & Zimmerman, B. J. (2012). *Motivation and self-regulated learning: Theory, research, and applications*. Routledge.
3. Young, D. J. (1999). A compelling case for the inclusion of emotional intelligence in foreign language pedagogy. *Foreign Language Annals*, 32(1), 48-58.
4. Zeidner, M., Matthews, G., & Roberts, R. D. (2009). *What we know about emotional intelligence: How it affects learning, work, relationships, and our mental health*. MIT Press.
5. Durlak, J. A., Weissberg, R. P., Dymnicki, A. B., Taylor, R. D., & Schellinger, K. B. (2011). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child Development*, 82(1), 405-432.
6. Rivers, S. E., Brackett, M. A., & Salovey, P. (2013). Emotional intelligence and academic achievement: What is the role of SEL in language learning? *Educational Psychologist*, 48(3), 111-130.
7. Kern, M. L., Benson, L., Steinberg, M., & Schein, C. (2016). Social and emotional learning in schools: From programs to practices. *The Future of Children*, 26(2), 61-72.
8. Greenberg, M. T., et al. (2003). The role of SEL in preventing school failure. *Social Policy Report*, 17(1), 4-15.
9. Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional Intelligence: Why It Can Matter More Than IQ*. Bantam Books.
10. Schutte, N. S., Malouff, J. M., Hall, L. E., Haggerty, D. J., Cooper, J. T., & Golden, C. J. (1998). Development and validation of a measure of emotional intelligence. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 25(2), 167-177.
11. Gardner, R. C. (1985). *Social psychology and second language learning: The role of attitudes and motivation*. London, UK: Edward Arnold.
12. Dörnyei, Z. (2001). *Motivation and second language acquisition*. Wiley-Blackwell.
13. Durlak, J. A., Domitrovich, C. E., & Weissberg, R. P. (2015). The impact of enhancing students' social and emotional learning: A meta-analysis of school-based universal interventions. *Child Development*, 82(1), 405-432.

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- 13.00.00 Pedagogika fanlari
 - 13.00.01 Pedagogika nazariyasi. Pedagogik ta'limotlar tarixi
 - 13.00.02 Ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi (sohalar bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.03 Maxsus pedagogika
 - 13.00.04 Jismoniy tarbiya va sport mashg'ulotlari nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.05 Kasb-hunar ta'limi nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.06 Elektron ta'lim nazariyasi va metodikasi (ta'lim sohaları va bosqichlari bo'yicha)
 - 13.00.07 Ta'limda menejment
 - 13.00.08 Maktabgacha ta'lim va tarbiya nazariyasi va metodikasi
 - 13.00.09 Ijtimoiy pedagogika
 - 07.00.00 Tarix fanlari
 - 19.00.00 Psixologiya fanlari
 - 01.00.00 Fizika-matematika fanlari
 - 02.00.00 Kimyo fanlari
 - 03.00.00 Biologiya fanlari
 - 09.00.00 Falsafa fanlari
 - 10.00.00 Filologiya fanlari
 - 11.00.00 Geografiya fanlari

MAKTABGACHA VA MAKTAB TA'LIMI

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